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Study of *Justicia carnea* leaf extract on Mild Steel Corrosion in Sulphuric acid medium by Gravimetric and Electrochemical Studies

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ABSTRACT

The inhibitive effect of *Justicia carnea* leaf extract on mild steel corrosion in 1M H₂SO₄ solution in 0.2 g/l – 0.8 g/l including the blank at immersion period of 2 h. to 24 h. was studied using electro chemical techniques and gravimetric method. The weight loss results showed drastic decrease in weight loss with increase in the concentration of the inhibitor, indicating that the plant extract was an excellent corrosion inhibitor. The introduction of the inhibitor to the steel also brought about reduction in the corrosion rate as compared with the blank. The inhibition efficiency increased with increase in concentration of the plant extract. The highest inhibition efficiency of 85.4% for 0.8 g/l of the extract in acidic medium was attained using both gravimetric method and impedance spectroscopy measurements. The values of charge transfer increased while the double layer capacitance values decrease with increasing *Justicia carnea* extract concentration. This indicates the formation of protective film. The immersion period did not show significant effect. The open circuit potential test showed that the potential of blank shifts toward the more negative values after 0 h, unlike the potential of inhibited steel that shifts to the less negative direction. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy data agreed with the polarization and open circuit potential results showing that *Justicia carnea* inhibited steels showed more surface and polarization resistances especially the highest concentration (0.8 g/l) and its surface was more passivated compared to the surface of blank sample.

Keywords: Anti-corrosion, *Justicia carnea*, Weight loss, Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, Polarization.

INTRODUCTION

Corrosion is one of the most common phenomena that we observe in our daily lives and it is caused by the contact of metal surface with dissolved carbon dioxide, hydrogen sulfide, as well as salts (Otaibi & Hammud 2021). The enormity of the cost of corrosion to the economy of any nation cannot be overemphasized. In addition to the huge cost, corrosion is also to be blamed for many of the disasters that cause the loss of life and devastating pollution of the environment (Adejo *et. al.*, 2019). In spite of much advancement in the field of corrosion science and engineering, the phenomenon of corrosion remains a

major challenge. To mitigate metal corrosion, effective inhibitors are necessary. Corrosion inhibitors are substance which when added in small concentration to corrosive media, decreases or prevent the reaction of the metal with the media. Inhibition of corrosion by adsorption inhibitors has been applied in different technologies such as acid pickling and descaling, petrochemicals, and storage of chemicals. Most of the effective and efficient organic Inhibitors are nitrogen, sulphure and phosphorous which allowed absorption in the metal surface (Zaferani et. al., 2013).

Although many synthetic compounds showed good anti - corrosive activity, most of them are highly toxic to both human beings and the environment (Raja & Sethuraman 2008). The known hazardous effect of most synthetic corrosion inhibitors are the motivation for the use of some natural products as corrosion inhibitors. Plant extracts have shown promise as sustainable and eco- friendly corrosion inhibitors (Fouda 2017). Plants can be effective corrosion inhibitors for mild steel due to the presence of compounds like tannins, alkaloids, flavonoids and organic acids like phenolic acids in their extract which these compounds and acids have been shown to exhibit corrosion inhibiting properties (Sahu 2020), (Chauhan, et. al., 2018) . These compounds can form a protective layer on the metal surface inhibiting the corrosion process (Singh et. al., 2020), (Tandon 2020) . Additionally, plants often have anti-oxidant property that helps in reducing the rate of corrosion by scavenging free radicals that promotes corrosion. The effectiveness of plant extracts as corrosion inhibitors depends on their chemical composition, concentration and their ability to interact with the metal surface and form a barrier against corrosive agents (Srivastava 2019).

This work is aimed at determining the inhibition effect of *Justicia carnea* on mild steel corrosion in 1.0 M H₂SO₄ solution. Mild steel was chosen in our studies since high temperature aggressive acids are widely used in industries in connection to mild and low alloy steels.

2.0 Experimental

2.1. Mild Steel Preparation

The spark analysis of the mild steel was carried out at Turret Engineering services LTD with specimens (F = 98.23 wt.%, Pd = 0.49 wt.%, Cu = 0.48 wt.%, Zn = 0.42 wt.%, and Mn = 0.38 wt.%) of dimensions of 20 x 20 x 1 mm were used for the gravimetric study. The weight, length, width and thicknesses of each of the coupons were measured too. These coupons were mechanically polished to remove coatings with Sic papers of different grades to obtain smooth surfaces that have no coatings on it. They were then degreased in ethanol, dried with acetone and stored in moisture free desiccators before being used for the studies.

2.2. Preparation of *Justicia carnea* Extract

Justicia carnea leaves were collected around umuazu Umuagubiam Owerri West L.G.A Imo State, Nigeria. The leaves were cleaned and air dried at room temperature for 5 days. Pulverized using a grinder, the grinded leaves were sieved to get smooth and uniform grains and 30 grams of it was soaked in distilled water. The crude extracts were boiled at 75⁰C in reflux apparatus for 3 hours, allowed to cool, and filtered. This procedure for the preparation of the leaf extracts is similar to that reported by (Owate et. al., 2014). 30g in 300ml of 1.0mol of H₂SO₄ of the inhibitor was used. Using refluxing method of extraction, the inhibitors were extracted. After filtration, a 36.68 g/l stock (extract) solution containing 9.17g of the leaves was obtained The amount of ground leaves material extracted into solution was quantified by comparing the weight of dried residue with initial weight of the dried leaf material before extraction. From the stock solutions which are the extracted dyes, a concentration range of 0.2 – 0.8 g/L was prepared including the blank, making it five concentrations and the exposure time for the coupons was for 24 hours, interval of 2 hours each. These were carried out at room temperature. All the 13 coupons used for the experiment were weighed before and after the immersion into the corrosive environment using JA 1003A electronic weighing balance with accuracy of ±0.005..Total immersion time was 24 hours, interval of 2hours each.

2.3. Gravimetric Technique

The mass-loss was calculated using the data obtained. Also from the values, The corrosion rate was calculated using the formula reportedly used by (Lebe & Owate 2015) as in the equation below:

$$CR = \frac{K\Delta W}{DA t} \quad 1$$

Where CR = corrosion rate in mils per year (mpy), ΔW = is the weight loss (g), D = metal density (g/cm³), A = area of the coupon (cm²), t = the time of exposure (h), K = constant (87.6).

inhibition efficiency (I%) was calculated using the following the equation:

$$I.E\% = \left(1 - \frac{CR_{inh}}{CR_{blank}}\right) \times 100 \quad 2$$

Where I.E% = represents the inhibition efficiency expressed in percentage, CR_{inh} = is the corrosion rate

in the presence of the inhibitor while CR_{blank} - is the corrosion rate in the absence of inhibitor

2.4 Electrochemical test

Electrochemical analyses were conducted in 1 M H₂SO₄ corrosive electrolyte. To prevent charging current and confirm system stability open circuit potential (OCP) was recorded for a duration of 1800 s (30 mins) on the blank and the optimum representative concentration of the inhibited system. This is required for the metal to dissolves at its equilibrium or free potential (E_{corr}) which is achieved at stable OCP. Thereafter, all the electrochemical experiments were carried out at OCP condition. The electrochemical tests were run using a cell assembly consisting of three electrodes which includes; 1 cm² exposed metal surface (mild steel) which served as the working electrode (WE), silver/silver chloride (Ag/AgCl) was used as a reference electrode (RE); all the reported potentials in this work are vs. Ag/AgCl, while platinum wire was utilized as a counter electrode (CE). The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was measured with a signal amplitude perturbation of 10 mV throughout a frequency range of 100 kHz–10 mHz. The potentiodynamic polarization investigation was conducted at the potential range of ± 250 mV versus OCP at scanning rate of 0.2 mV s⁻¹. The data were later analyzed using appropriate electrochemical analytical softwares such as Zsimpwin 3.2 model and Metrohm Autolab PGSTAT 204 for EIS with the fitted equivalent circuit simulated for the specific metal/ electrolyte environment and EC-lab was utilized for the potentiodynamic polarization, analyses. The Potentiodynamic polarization testing were conducted to measure the corrosion parameters such as corrosion potential (E_{Corr}), corrosion current (j_{Corr}), polarization resistance (R_p) and corrosion rate (R_{Corr}) for mild steel of both blank and inhibited steel after immersion in the H₂SO₄ solution from 2 h. to 24 h. in 4 different concentrations, including the blank. The values of cathodic (β_c) and anodic (β_a) Tafel slope, corrosion potential (E_{Corr}), corrosion current density (j_{Corr}), polarization resistance (R_p), and corrosion rate (R_{Corr}) obtained for mild steel electrode from the polarization curves was shown, including the table . The values of (β_c) and (β_a) were determined after at least 10 mV away from E_{Corr} and at least one decade of current densities (j_{Corr}). The values of E_{Corr} and j_{Corr} were obtained from the extrapolation of anodic and cathodic Tafel lines located next to the linearized current regions. The values of polarization resistance, R_p , for steel (blank) and different concentration of justicia carnea were calculated as reported in (Eduok et.al., 2012), corrosion work as follows:

$$R_p = 1/j_{corr} = \frac{1}{j_{corr}} \left(\frac{B_c \cdot B_a}{2.3 (B_c + B_a)} \right) \quad 3$$

$$R_{corr} = \frac{j_{corr} k \cdot E_w}{d A} \quad 4$$

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Gravimetric Studies (Mass- Loss Measurement)

Fig 1 : shows the variation in weight loss against exposure time for mild steel in H₂SO₄ medium without and with different concentrations of *Justicia carnea* leaves extracts. From the graph, it is evident that without the inhibitor, the weight loss is high but as inhibitor is introduced, the weight loss reduced. This result is in agreement with results of Corrosion (Iyasara & Oviri 2015), (Avwiri & Igho 2003), (Owate et.al., 2014) though we cannot clearly ascertain the strength of the increase in the concentration of the inhibitor with respect to exposure time, if we do not remove the blank.

Fig.1: the graph of weight loss (g) Vs Exposure time for mild steel in H₂SO₄ medium with and without blank.

Fig. 2 shows the difference in weight loss against exposure time for mild steel in H_2SO_4 medium with different concentrations of *Justicia carnea* leaves extracts without the blank. It is obvious that the more a metal loses weight in a medium, the more corrosive the medium is. But as the inhibitor is introduced, the rate in which the metal loses weight reduces. From the results, increase in the concentration of inhibitor reduces the weight loss of the mild steel. It was also observed that 0.4g/l concentration was not stable. It fluctuates up and down with respect to the time exposure. The effect of time did not show any significant effect in these results while the higher the concentration of the inhibitor, the less the weight loss, indicating that (*Justicia carnea*) is a good inhibitor in H_2SO_4 . These are in accordance with results of (Avwiri & Igho 2003), (Owate et.at., 2014) .

Fig. 2 : Time dependence of the weight loss (g) of samples in the studied environments

Fig. 3 shows the graph of the corrosion rate against the concentrations of the inhibitor. Inspection of the figures revealed that the corrosion rate of mild steel in 1.0M H_2SO_4 solution was reduced upon the introduction of *Justicia carnea* leaves extracts into the corrosive medium. The extent of reduction in corrosion rate is seen to increase with increase in the concentration of the *Justicia carnea* extracts. From the results, it also showed as the time increases, the rate of corrosion reduces, though it did not reveal quiet outstanding significance. This result is in accordance with that of (Adejo et.al., 2019), (Lebe & Owate 2015).

Fig.3: Concentration dependence of the Corrosion rates (mpy) of samples of *Justicia carnea* in H₂SO₄.

Fig.4 shows the plot of the inhibition efficiency against extract concentration from weight loss experiments. Close examination of the results showed that the leaves extracts of *Justicia carnea* afforded protection for mild steel in 1M H₂SO₄ solution which could be attributed to the adsorption of the components of the extracts on the mild steel surface. The effect of time showed little significance but not outstanding. It was also observed that the higher the concentration, the higher the inhibition efficiency. Generally the average inhibition efficiency of this result is above 70% indicating that the leaf extracts of *Justicia carnea* inhibited well on the mild steel in H₂SO₄. This result is in agreement with results of (Adejo et.al., 2019), (Lebe & Owate 2015), (Owate et. al., 2014).

Fig 4 : the graph of the Inhibition Eff. vs different concentration of the Inhibitor

Fig.5 shows the potential-time curves obtained for mild steel in 1 M of H_2SO_4 solution in both blank and inhibited sample. The blank curve showed decrease in the more negative direction at 0 s to 400 s showing that the steel was not attack by H_2SO_4 at zero seconds but as time increases the potential then slightly shifted in the more negative direction with increasing time till the end of the experiment. This more negative shift might have resulted from the dissolution of steel by the sulphuric acid attack. On the other hand, introducing inhibitor positively shifted the free potential for the mild steel. Further increase in the immersion time did not alter it rather it maintained a horizontal curve towards the noble potential direction, which resulted by the thickening of the formed oxide and/or the development of corrosion products on the steel surface. Such oxide and corrosion products provide partial protection against corrosion of steel in 1 M of H_2SO_4 solution. The potential-time behavior for steel indicates that the surface of justicia carnea inhibited steel is more corrosion resistant than the mild steel without inhibitor at the same conditions. This agrees with the data obtained by (Eduok *et. al.*, 2012).

Fig .5: Open circuit potential (OCP) analysis of mild steel for blank uninhibited system in comparison with Justicia Carnea inhibited, tested in 1 M H₂SO₄ corrosive environment at room temperature.

Fig.6 showed the Potentiodynamic polarization curves of mild steel immersed in 1 M H₂SO₄ acid environment in the absence and presence of inhibitor. The corrosion parameters namely corrosion potential (E_{corr}), corrosion current density (I_{corr}), Tafel slopes (b_a & b_c), corrosion rate (CR) and inhibition efficiency (IE%) are given in table 1. E_{corr} values shifted to positive potential with increase in concentrations of Justicia carnea leaf extract. The corrosion current densities reduced from 1881 μ A to 275 μ A with increase in concentration of the inhibitor. There is also a notable difference in the E_{corr} range (-700 mV to -690 mV) attained in the absence and presence of inhibitor. The plots showed linear shape at lower current densities due to protective layer formed on the metal surface and decreased the transfer of electrons at the interface. The protection can be attributed due to the nitrogen atom which donates the lone pair of electrons to surface of the metal for easy adsorption and hence reduces the corrosion rate. The maximum inhibition efficiency was found to be 85.4% in 1 M H₂SO₄ at 0.8 g/l concentration of inhibitor at room temperature. Inhibition efficiency increased with increasing inhibitor concentration and also decreased rate of corrosion. These results are in agreement with the results of (Subasree *et. al.*, 2018).

Table 1. Potentiodynamic polarization (PDP) parameters relating to mild steel for blank uninhibited system in comparison with Justicia Carnea inhibited, tested in 1 M H₂SO₄ corrosive environment at room temperature.

System	E_{corr}	I_{corr}	β_a	β_c	θ	IE
	mV/Ag/AgCl	μAcm^{-2}	mVdec ⁻¹	mVdec ⁻¹	-	%
Blank ((1 M H ₂ SO ₄)	-700	1881	88	165	-	-
0.2 g/L	-730	1662	71	160	0.116	11.6
0.4 g/L	-720	1010	55	131	0.463	46.3
0.6 g/L	-710	605	88	88	0.678	67.8
0.8 g/L	-690	275	89	66	0.854	85.4

Fig.6 . Potentiodynamic polarization (PDP) analysis of mild steel for blank uninhibited system in comparison with Justicia carnea inhibited, tested in 1 M H₂SO₄ corrosive environment at room temperature.

Fig .7 showed The Nyquist plot obtained for blank and justicia carnea inhibited mild steel electrodes at their open-circuit potential after their immersion in 1 M H₂SO₄ solutions from 2 h to 24 h .The Nyquist plot reveals that increasing the concentration of inhibitor causes an increase in both the diameter of the

semicircles and the R_{ct} values as shown in table 2. Hence an increase in the corrosion inhibition efficiency. From the ohmic law where $V = iR$, the higher the resistance value (R_{ct}), the lower the electrical current (i) flow, the lower the number of electrons transferred across the metal surface. Thus, oxidation of steel is inhibited (Otaibi & Hammud 2021), (Subasree *et. al.*, 2018).

The surface coverage θ increases from 0.00 at blank (uninhibited) to 0.854 at the highest concentration 0.8 g/l. At low inhibitor concentration the inhibitor is selective and bind specifically to active surface sites that would be most vulnerable to corrosion initiation. But as the inhibitor concentration increases to an optimum value, a protective layer form with more coverage area is achieved. This is in accordance with results of (Otaibi & Hammud 2021).

Table 2. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) data relating to mild steel for blank uninhibited system in comparison with Justicia carnea inhibited, tested in 1 M H₂SO₄ corrosive environment at room temperature.

System	R_s ($\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$)	R_{po} ($\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$)	$Q1 \times 10^{-5}$ ($\mu\Omega^{-1} s^n$ cm^{-2})	n1	R_{ct} (Ω cm^2)	$Q2 \times 10^{-5}$ ($\mu\Omega^{-1} s^n$ cm^{-2})	n1	θ	IE %
Blank (1 M H ₂ SO ₄)	20.01	30	240.2	0.86	200	14.25	0.82	-	-
0.2 g/L	19.66	40	95.0	0.88	210	11.12	0.89	0.08	8.0
0.4 g/L	21.1	50	87.1	0.89	400	10.61	0.89	0.489	48.9
0.6 g/L	20.3	60	54.5	0.93	550	8.97	0.97	0.623	62.3
0.8 g/L	21.8	80	22.6	0.98	1040	8.51	0.98	0.795	79.5

Fig.7 : Nyquist plot for electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) analysis of mild steel for blank uninhibited system in comparison with *Justicia carnea* inhibited, tested in 1 M H_2SO_4 corrosive environment at room temperature.

Fig. 8: Bode plots (a) modulus and (b) phase angle for electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) analysis of mild steel for blank uninhibited system in comparison with *Justicia carnea* inhibited, tested in 1 M H_2SO_4 corrosive environment at room temperature.

Fig. 9: Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) data relating to mild steel for the effects of temperature variations on *Justicia carnea* inhibited, tested in 1 M H_2SO_4 corrosive environment.

CONCLUSION

The influence of *Justicia carnea* plant extract on the corrosion of mild steel was investigated in Sulphuric acid medium. The work was carried out using gravimetry studies and a variety of electrochemical measurements, including potentiodynamic polarization, open-circuit potential (OCP) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). It has been found that blank recorded higher anodic, cathodic and corrosion currents and corrosion rate with lower corrosion resistance compared to the inhibited samples at the same conditions.

From the gravimetric results obtained it could be concluded that increase in the concentration of *Justicia carnea* leaf extracts, brought about decrease in the weight-loss and corrosion rate of the mild steel in 1 M H_2SO_4 environment. *Justicia carnea* leaf extract showed increase in inhibition efficiency with increase in inhibitor concentration. It showed maximum inhibition efficiency of 85.4% for 0.8 g/l of the extract. The immersion period did not show significant effect. The OCP test showed that the potential of blank shifts toward the more negative values after 0 h, unlike the potential of inhibited steel that shifts to the less negative direction. EIS data agreed with the polarization and OCP results showing that *Justicia carnea* inhibited steels showed more surface and polarization resistances especially the highest concentration (0.8 g/l) and its surface was more passivated compared to the surface of blank.

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